

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF WHATSAPP USAGE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING VOCABULARY AT THE TERTIARY LEVEL

Sawera Liaquat¹, Asadullah Balouch^{*2}

¹MS Scholar, Centre of English Language & Linguistics, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology Jamshoro, Pakistan

^{*2}PhD Scholar (English Linguistics), University of Sindh Jamshoro;
Lecturer, Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad

¹kzsawera826@gmail.com, ^{*2}asadullahbalouch@sbbusba.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *
Asadullah Balouch

Abstract

The current study, using Koole and Ally's (2006) FRAME model, investigated the influence of WhatsApp as a vocabulary learning and teaching tool at the tertiary level. Viewing technological progressions, the dramatic expansion of social networking applications like WhatsApp can be employed to facilitate EFL learners to develop their vocabulary. This study used a quasi-experimental design in which the researchers' divided participants into two groups, namely controlled and experimental. Thereafter, the randomly selected research sample (n=40) from BS Part I was classified into two equal groups which were experimental and controlled (n=20) from the Department of English, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad (SBBU, SBA). The control group was taught vocabulary using the traditional method, while the experimental group was taught those words using WhatsApp for six weeks. The participants from both groups were taught and given assignments of new words. The participants of the experimental group (n=20) completed their assignments of making sentences with each new word by using a dictionary for meaning and submitting via WhatsApp. On the other hand, the participants of the control group completed the same homework assignments using the paper-pencil method. The results revealed that the experimental group significantly outperformed in comparison with the control group in the completion of vocabulary learning tasks. Moreover, the results of the questionnaire gauged participants' perceptions towards the WhatsApp application while learning vocabulary which shows the participants have a positive attitude towards learning new words using WhatsApp. Considering the findings, the study found that the use of WhatsApp has a constructive and significant effect on EFL learners' vocabulary development.

INTRODUCTION

In line with technological advancements, the inevitable advantage of educational apps using mobile phones as a gadget has largely facilitated ESL learners. Likewise, WhatsApp as a social media app is widely used by ESL learners for developing

language skills in general and developing vocabulary in particular. This study mainly concerns how struggling ESL learners with slow vocabulary growth and poor reading comprehension may develop their vocabulary using WhatsApp. The adoption of this

technological tool as an instructional platform has become more widespread in many organizations. It encourages quicker and simpler interaction between learners and develops their capacity to cooperate in a group chat on the topics. WhatsApp is a messaging app is a platform that brings together all participants, including instructors and students.

1.1. Background of the study

One of the essential components of learning a second language is acquiring vocabulary. To master in second language one must get the knowledge of vocabulary. The issue is that English language learners cannot communicate with people or understand written texts if they do not have a sufficient vocabulary. It is important to find the appropriate strategy for learning a second language vocabulary to get a grip on language proficiency. In the Pakistani context, English is used as a second language or a foreign language, students are struggling to acquire the language for the academic burgeoning. Thus, this study is conducted to examine and suggest a better way to impart knowledge of new words. The few studies that have looked into how WhatsApp affects vocabulary learning have not produced any clear-cut conclusions. Fageeh (2013) conducted one of the earlier investigations at a Saudi college, looking at the outcomes of practising WhatsApp for learning new words to ESL learners in a semester. Findings from the post-test of the study revealed a significant difference between the control and experimental groups. In the WhatsApp group, vocabulary test scores were much higher. The influence of using WhatsApp in the Turkish class setting was also investigated. Basal, Sari, Yilmaz and Tanverdi (2016) compared the efficiency of WhatsApp in acquiring idioms from traditional classroom activities to the Michigan Corpus of Academic Spoken English. The post-test results showed that individuals in the experimental group performed better than those in the control group. The study showed that the integration of WhatsApp in learning idioms has positively impacted and increased learners' ability to understand idioms. Hence, there is a need to further investigate the potential of conducting more studies on vocabulary teaching and learning through WhatsApp, especially in Pakistan.

1.2. Research objectives

The current study proposes:

RO1: To examine WhatsApp effect as a learning tool for learning and teaching vocabulary at the tertiary level

RO2: To determine students' opinions towards WhatsApp to develop L2 vocabulary

1.3. Research Questions

RQ1: What effect does WhatsApp have as a learning tool for learning and teaching vocabulary at the tertiary level?

RQ2: What are the students' opinions towards the usage of WhatsApp to enhance their knowledge in learning?

1.4. Research Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant difference between the students of the control group and those who learn vocabulary using WhatsApp.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference between the students of the control group and those who learn vocabulary using WhatsApp.

1.5. Significance of the study

Vocabulary is the most important language unit for students to master at the beginning of their English studies. The vocabulary of any language helps the learner to express their thoughts clearly. However, this study allows teachers and learners to adopt WhatsApp as a learning instrument. And make WhatsApp reliable for acquiring vocabulary for EFL learners. WhatsApp application proved its ability to motivate the students of ESL and helps to boost their confidence in completing the task, which is required during the learning process. This study provides a way of acquiring vocabulary for academic settings in a more preferable media. WhatsApp is used as a successful teaching and learning platform across many countries.

2.1. Literature Review

The study has shed light on the impact of using WhatsApp on vocabulary learning. This study compares the traditional technique of teaching second language vocabulary to WhatsApp to examine how EFL students' vocabulary grows over time. Numerous researches have examined the impact of

WhatsApp on participants' improvement in English language acquisition (Ali & Bin-Hady, 2019). Thus, expanding vocabulary knowledge is one of the key requirements for language learning, which can only be done when teachers employ excellent strategies for teaching and learning vocabulary. Mobile devices have critical stability as a tool for learning which motivates students to learn because those devices are frequently utilized by learners in daily life. It raises their vocabulary acquisition proficiency for ESL. Mobile devices promote the students' engagement during learning because of their interesting features, students get involved in the tasks and activities.

To create a vocabulary enhancement environment, an instructor searches for the best strategy that grasps pupils' attention and focus. MALL can improve students' confidence in developing communication through new words. Successful communication is resisted by limited vocabulary in a second language. Therefore, vocabulary knowledge is often seen as a necessary skill for second language learners. Some scholars contend that for readers of second languages to comprehend academic publications adequately, they must be familiar with more than 90% of the vocabulary used (Hirsh & Nation, 1992; Groot, 1994; Hazenberg & Hulstijn, 1996; Laufer, 1989). The never-ending search for effective vocabulary teaching has been an ongoing interest to language teachers since vocabulary learning is important in achieving competence in a language and priority for language learners (Caudy & Huckin, 1997). Thorn Burry thinks that students who spend a lot of time studying grammar won't advance very far in their language learning, but students who learn more vocabulary and phrases will advance more quickly because grammar can only say a small portion of what you can say with words. Making vocabulary learning a priority for any institution teaching foreign languages is conceivable (Tanaka, 2017). The importance of vocabulary is indicated daily in and out of the school. The students who possess more vocabulary knowledge achieve higher than those who have less knowledge about new words. In English as a Second Language (ESL) and English as a Foreign Language (ESL) learning vocabulary items play a vital role in all language skills (i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing). There has recently been a marked 16 increase in studies on teaching vocabulary

as a result of the importance put on L2 vocabulary development. As a result, both researcher and practitioner are actively looking for strategies and techniques to increase learning and retention of vocabulary knowledge effectively. As a result, WhatsApp is seen as a useful tool for language acquisition, and various language institutions employ it. Abualrob & Nazzal (2020) also stated that WhatsApp provides a platform for both the teachers and the students to interact and express their knowledge and ideas openly. This application is reliable to adopt for every person as it is free of cost. Therefore, WhatsApp is considered to be an effective teaching tool that provides a positive impact on students' achievements in academics. When we have ideas and concepts and we want to express the only way to convey them is stored vocabulary that makes it fluently possible. Without an extensive vocabulary, we are unable to use the structures and functions we have learned for comprehensible communication. Therefore acquisition of lexical knowledge is essential in EFL and ESL learning. Using WhatsApp can help EFL learners learn more vocabulary items because it has many interesting features through which the instructor can make it easier to build a learning environment (i.e. group chatting, sending videos, audio, pictures links to different websites and document files). WhatsApp is employed in higher education. It is used for the improvement of the exchange of opinions and data among the instructors and their students.

Since Internet-based technology is the popular topic that today's students are most familiar with, they can develop the skills they need to direct the creation of their knowledge actively. WhatsApp is one of those tools which have been used as the generally used social platform or community on mobile devices and computers (Yeboah & Ewur, 2014). WhatsApp appears to be the most outstanding application among social media. One of the most widely used social networks worldwide, especially among young people, is WhatsApp. Researchers and English language instructors from all over the world have conducted studies to find out whether WhatsApp is a reliable language-learning instrument or not. This is because WhatsApp provides a platform for both teachers and students to interact and express their knowledge and ideas openly (Abualrob & Nazzal,

2020). Further, WhatsApp contains many features such as audio and video recording, taking pictures, sending media files and documents, surfing the internet and many more that support teaching and learning (Boyinbode, Agbonifo & Ogundare, 2017). One of the most widely used social networks worldwide, especially among young people, is WhatsApp. Researchers and English language instructors from all over the world have conducted studies to find out whether WhatsApp is a reliable language-learning instrument or not. This is because WhatsApp provides a platform for both teachers and students to interact and express their knowledge and ideas openly (Abualrob & Nazzal, 2020). Further, WhatsApp contains many features such as audio and video recording, taking pictures, sending media files and documents, surfing the internet and many more that support teaching and learning (Boyinbode, Agbonifo & Ogundare, 2017).

It is intensely common and convenient to use because people can communicate with their friends through WhatsApp. Many people downloaded the WhatsApp application on various types of mobile including iPhone, Nokia, Android and Blackberry. It enables the user to communicate online with one another for free.

Additionally, users can exchange images, audio files, and movies. WhatsApp offers a variety of features to send and receive messages between groups and individuals, which include text messages, audio files, video files, attached photographs and links to any websites. Similarly, Vygotsky's Constructive Learning Theory is suitable for WhatsApp usage in this new phenomenon. Therefore, this application has become increasingly popular over the last two years with 350 million users (Cohavi, 2013). Alik and Bensalem (2018) investigated the impact of WhatsApp on learners' vocabulary learning. Bensalem suggests that WhatsApp can be used as a serviceable didactic tool in teaching and learning. His research shows that the application offers the novelty of experience, a sense of immediacy, and a sense of belonging. These factors influence students' motivation to learn and memorise new words. It is proven that to build a successful vocabulary stock, WhatsApp can be a great platform to be adopted. As many researchers stated the advantages of MALL and WhatsApp applications are the most commonly used

strategies in current educational trends, this study also focuses on vocabulary learning via WhatsApp and how students perceive this application as a learning tool. Learning vocabulary online is more attractive and useful for students. It helps to improve English learners' motivation and vocabulary learning, it attracts students' attention and self-confidence. Therefore, WhatsApp is recommended for EFL learning.

2.2 Theoretical framework

This study used Koole and Ally's (2006) Framework for the Rational Analysis of Mobile Education (FRAME) model that visualizes mobile learning as the intersection of three features: the device, the learner and the social environment. This model is useful to inspect how WhatsApp as a social networking tool develops not only learner's autonomy but also language skills. This study mainly examines the impact of WhatsApp on the development of EFL learners' vocabulary.

3.1. Research Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design. Macburney & White (2007) stated that quasi-experiment research design is the procedure in which the scientist must select subjects for different conditions from different conditions from preexisting groups.

3.2. Research Participants, Sampling Strategy and Site

Employing purposive sampling, the study drew a sample of (n=40) BS Part I majoring in English from SBBU SBA. The research participants were equally divided into the ratio of (n=20) for the experimental and controlled groups respectively. However, the participants' age range was from 19 to 22.

3.3. Research Instrument.

This study used the pre-test, and post-test (see Appendix C) to scrutinize the students' knowledge about the subject, an adapted questionnaire (see Appendix A) to measure the students' opinions and the WhatsApp Application as a learning platform.

3.4. Pre-test and post-test

Pre-tests and post-tests were designed to examine the practicability of WhatsApp for vocabulary teaching and learning in the experimental and controlled treatments. This study used a list of 14 words for a pre-test on vocabulary. Both the experimental and control groups take a pre-test to determine the vocabulary proficiency of the students before the treatment.

The students can select the right response by using the vocabulary in fill-in-the-blank and definition-matching formats. The experiment is carried out for six (6) weeks, whereby ten (10) words are sent via WhatsApp and ten (10) in traditional classrooms during the trial. To assess the final result of this research, all teaching and learning activities will be conducted using two different techniques (traditional and WhatsApp). The instructor served as the facilitator as the students used WhatsApp to discuss the vocabulary, give definitions, share pronunciations, and build sentences. By the end of each lesson, the lecturer catered vocabulary exercises for the students.

Note: see Appendix A for the Pre-test and Post-test

3.5. Questionnaire

The questionnaire was adapted from the previous study by Bensalem (2018). The purpose of the questionnaire is to investigate the extent of the use of mobile technology by students of the English department at SBBU SBA to learn advanced English vocabulary. The questions are comprehensive enough to interpret and easy for the students to understand the goal of the research, ensuring that they will receive the correct answers. The Likert scale is more appropriate for measuring participants' views or opinions regarding the topic of the subject. The fifteen closed questions are the fifteen closed items that used a five-point Likert scale to rate the opinions of students. From 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) and it consists of 15 sequentially organized questions separated into three sections that focus: Learners' persuasion regarding the utilization of WhatsApp in the teaching and learning process, their experience of learning with the WhatsApp application and learners' attitudes towards using

Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) in the pedagogical process.

In the experimental group, the survey is carried out using WhatsApp as a tool and following certain procedures.

3.6. Data collection procedure

The objective of the investigation was explained to the participants who were taking part in this study at the beginning of the experiment. Pre-tests on English vocabulary were given to the students in the control and experimental groups. The same list of sixty words is given to the experimental and control groups over the six-week course with an equitable quantity of ten words in a week. The classes planned according to its timetable, are held once a week for 45 to 60 minutes. After the teacher separates the class into two groups, the students of the experimental group get to follow WhatsApp to learn the word lists.

The participants in the traditional group were given a paper-form vocabulary chart during class. The congruence with the regularity of class meetings, the vocabulary list will be distributed once each week.

The assignments focus on finding out the definition of a new word with the help of monolingual dictionaries and creating sentences on those words. The experimental group chose free monolingual dictionary apps to check the meaning of the new words.

The participants took part in an unexpected vocabulary post-test after completing all assigned homework (of six weeks of learning) at the lesson when the last assignment was checked out. The post-objective tests were to measure how much the students' vocabulary has grown. The written record was conducted to ascertain which approach improves students' capacity to learn new terminology the most. Pre-test and post-test both have the same format and content. To prevent students from memorizing the right answers, the researcher has rearranged the items. At the end of the trial, the students in the experimental group were required to answer a questionnaire on how they believe using WhatsApp has helped them learn new vocabulary.

4.1. Results and Discussion

The experiment group produces the result consisting of two parts. The first part indicates the result of a pre-test. The second one shows the result of the post-test. The Researcher used SPSS software to analyse and measure the mean and standard deviations of

the results.

4.2. Results of the pre-test

Firstly, an independent sample t-test was used to see if the differences in the pre-test mean between the control (traditional) and experimental (WhatsApp) groups were significant before treatment.

Table 1

Comparing The Results Of The Pre-Test Between WhatsApp and Traditional Group

Groups	N	mean	Std. deviation
Control group	Pre-test = 20	4.9875	1.50978
Experimental group	Pre-test = 20	5.6875	2.12361
Mean difference		0.7	

It shows that the pre-test mean score is a little higher among the students in the WhatsApp group than the students in the paper-based group (5.6875, 4.9875).

Table 2

Comparing The Result Of The Post-Test Between The Control And WhatsApp Group

Groups		N	mean	Std. deviation
Control group	Post-test	= 20	7.4375	1.52582
Experimental group	Post-test	= 20	10.2125	2.14334
Mean difference	-		2.775	

It is apparent from the table that the scores are significantly higher in the experimental group (m =10.2125, Std. =2.14334) than in the control group (m=7.4375, Std. =1.52582). The findings show that utilizing WhatsApp to learn English for first-year students is more appealing, more efficient, and more beneficial for picking up new vocabulary than

traditional learning.

4.3. Comparison of pre-and post-test results.

A paired samples t-test was carried out to look into the extent of improvement in each group from the pre-test to the post-test. The results of the pre-and post-test are presented to show the descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for both groups in Table 3.

Table 3

Comparison of Pre- and Post-test Mean scores of students in both Groups.

Groups		Pre-test (N= 20)	Post-test (N=20)
Paper-based	Mean	4.9875	7.4375
(Control group)	Std	1.50978	1.52582
WhatsApp group	Mean	5.6875	10.2125
(experimental group)	Std	2.12361	2.14334

Before the intervention, the mean score of the student's vocabulary in the traditional paper-based(control) group and WhatsApp(experimental) group were 4.9875 and 7.4375 out of 15 points.

After the intervention, these scores rose to 5.6875 and 10.2125, respectively. The standard deviation of the two groups also increased a little bit. From the data obtained based on the independent t-test

analysis, the post-test results are significantly higher than the pre-test mean scores in both groups. Thus, it can be concluded that the participants of both groups in this experiment developed their vocabulary knowledge.

However, the learners who were using WhatsApp obtained more vocabulary than those whose instruction involved traditional paper-based techniques.

4.3.1. Evaluation of the students' questionnaire

After the completion of the treatment, students in the experimental group were allowed to express their thoughts on vocabulary acquisition via WhatsApp.

There were 15 logical items in the questionnaire. They are measured on a five-point Likert scale (from 1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree).

At the end of the study, views of the students toward the creative use of MALL with a special priority to WhatsApp, were examined using analysis of quantitative data acquired from the questionnaire given to the WhatsApp group participants. The means and standard deviations of the results were examined. A mean score of 1-1.50 described an attitude at a very negative level, 1.51-2.50 at a negative level, 2.51-3.50 at a moderate level, 3.51-4.50 at a positive level, and 4.51-5.00 at a very positive level.

Table 4. Questionnaire for assessment of the student’s opinions and perceptions regarding WhatsApp.

Statements	N	Mean	Std. deviation	Level
Q 1	20	3.95	1.432	Positive
Q 2	20	4.15	1.309	Positive
Q 3	20	4.15	.988	Positive
Q 4	20	3.40	.940	Moderate
Q 5	20	3.80	1.361	Positive
Q 6	20	4.55	.605	Very positive
Q 7	20	3.90	1.373	Positive
Q 8	20	4.65	.587	Very positive
Q 9	20	3.55	1.432	Positive
Q 10	20	3.90	1.071	Positive
Q 11	20	4.30	1.218	Positive
Q 12	20	4.50	1.051	Positive
Q 13	20	4.10	1.071	Positive
Q 14	20	4.35	.813	Positive
Q 15	20	4.45	.686	Positive

Table 4 demonstrates that students' overall perception of using mobile applications was favourable. When each question is taken into consideration, it was discovered that Q.6 (Writing sentences including the new words and sending them to the instructor via WhatsApp is a useful activity.) and Q.8 (With the help of mobile we can learn many things at a time.) obtained the highest marks (4.55, 4.65). In light of this data, it is a little surprise that Q.4 had the lowest results (if given the choice between using WhatsApp and the paper and pencil method of learning in future, I would choose using WhatsApp). Results from the questionnaire (Q.1 to Q.15) depicted a positive attitude containing

scores between 3.51 and 4.50, which shows students' interest in WhatsApp learning. Appendix A includes the complete questionnaire.

4.4. Discussion

The current study discovered that teaching vocabulary through WhatsApp is important for students to learn effectively. The main goal of the study was to determine which method (WhatsApp (experimental) or paper-based) is more effective in helping the students in their first year in the English department at SBBU SBA to develop their vocabulary proficiency. The findings of the experiment demonstrate that both groups'

vocabulary knowledge increased. How the students learned affected their test results. Following the treatment, the pupils in the experiment group outperformed those in the more conventional paper-based group in terms of academic performance.

The results of this study are consistent with those of earlier investigations into WhatsApp's effects. Bensalem (2018), Tai, Ting (2011), Alhavit (2015), and others looked at how the integration of WhatsApp in learning affects users' proficiency in knowledge of new vocabulary. Similar results were reported by Gutiérrez-Colon (2013) who studied the benefits of using WhatsApp to improve the English reading skills of Spanish college students. The study's findings showed that practically all participating students agreed that using WhatsApp increased their interest towards reading in English. Previous studies have shown the great impact of the mobile application in teaching and learning vocabulary. Therefore, this study mainly focused on how WhatsApp will influence the students of ESL to boost their ability to learn vocabulary, what are their opinions regarding the usage of this application and how much will they perform better while using this App in learning second language vocabulary. The findings of the study indicate the link between students in the experimental groups scoring better on post-tests and their use of WhatsApp applications. The use of WhatsApp to create a flexible learning environment where students may choose their study times and places may be one explanation for these results. The findings of this study are significant in at least two important ways. They first show how adding learning with WhatsApp to the teaching process improves students' vocabulary knowledge. Second, the students have a positive opinion of using smartphone apps. Researcher found the positive results similar to the many studies got previously. In the last decade, there was a significant emergence in using MALL in second language learning. It shows the rapid adoption of such strategies for ESL learners. Learners and practitioners are using a strategy that is reliable enough to help them to have comprehensive learning. WhatsApp is one of those applications which has proved as a useful source that enhances the motivation of students to learn second language vocabulary. It is the modern way to teach with

mobile devices and it is easy to use by learners and teachers. Mobile phones have different features that help the students to comprehend the tasks. Therefore, the study reveals how the learners enjoyed adopting WhatsApp as their learning platform. This study also examined to what extent the WhatsApp application in teaching and learning vocabulary in ESL classes improves learners' capacity to acquire vocabulary and what are the students' feedback about using WhatsApp. The findings show positive results of using the WhatsApp strategy in ESL classes as compared to the traditional method of teaching and learning.

5.1. Conclusion

Mobile devices which are regularly used by learners in everyday life offer a significantly plausible learning tool for encouraging students to learn. Their ability to acquire vocabulary for ESL increases as a result.

Vo and Jatrapitakkul (2016) claim that the importance of vocabulary in language learning and instruction may be seen in the way that it improves students' communication skills. Some scholars contend that for readers of second languages to comprehend academic publications adequately, they must be familiar with more than 90% of the vocabulary used. Research on vocabulary learning has dramatically increased as a result of the importance placed on L2 vocabulary knowledge. As a result, both academics and professionals are actively searching for methods and tactics to improve vocabulary learning and retention. Many language institutions use WhatsApp because it is considered to be a helpful tool for language learning.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine whether imparting vocabulary to students via WhatsApp will enhance learners' vocabulary as compared to more traditional approaches. Everyone has a personal cell phone and they are more likely to learn by using the various applications on their phones. One of them is WhatsApp, which allows learners to practice their language skills. The effectiveness of WhatsApp as a language learning tool has been investigated by academics and teachers of English around the world. A study was conducted by AbdAlfattah (2015) to determine whether using WhatsApp Messenger as a mobile learning strategy may improve students' writing abilities. Results

showed that in comparison to the control group, the WhatsApp strategy had a positive impact on the experimental group. Furthermore, this study has shown the positive impact of usage of the WhatsApp to teach and learn new vocabulary among the students of SBBU SBA. This data was collected by quantitative research design with a six-week long learning and teaching process where sixty(60) vocabulary were taught. Pre-test and post-test were used to differentiate the students' knowledge regarding words. Fifteen (15) questions are designed to conclude the students' attitude towards learning with the WhatsApp application. After collecting the data, its mean and standard deviation were measured through SPSS software. It was found that the results of the post-test were higher than the pre-test. Moreover, students have a positive view of learning vocabulary through WhatsApp.

5.2. Limitations and Future Studies

It is necessary to address the current study's limitations. First, to gauge how effectively the experiment participants can retain the words they learned, tests should be given at least a few weeks after the research procedure is over. Secondly, the study's centre of attention is on vocabulary in general. If idioms and other language groupings are used, objectives and goals will be accomplished. Finally, the researcher had no control over how long each group spent working on the vocabulary activities during the study. The results of the research may be impacted by the increased effort of some participants.

More studies are required to explore and understand the effects of using WhatsApp for vocabulary learning at many skill levels. Future studies should investigate the impact of WhatsApp on learners' vocabulary retention. A few weeks after the experiment is over, students should be analyzed specifically to see how well they can remember the words they learn. Furthermore, it will be useful to focus on more than one language learning skill via WhatsApp, such as listening and speaking, reading and writing strategies.

6. References

- Ahmed, S. T. S. (2019). Chat and learn: Effectiveness of using WhatsApp as a pedagogical tool to enhance EFL learners reading and writing skills. *International Journal of English Language and Literature Studies*, 8(2), 61-68.
- Alenazi, A. A. (2018). WhatsApp Messenger as a Learning Tool: An Investigation of Pre-Service Teachers' Learning without Instructor Presence. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 6(1), 1-8.
- Alsaleem, B.I.A. (2014). The effect of WhatsApp electronic dialogue journal on improving writing vocabulary word choice and voice of EFL undergraduate Saudi students. *Arab World English Journal*, 4(3), 213-225.
- Başal, A, Aytan, T. & Demir, I. (2016). Teaching Vocabulary with Graphic Novels. *English Language Teaching*, Vol. 9, No. 9; 2016.
- Bensalem, E. (2018). The Impact of WhatsApp on EFL Students' Vocabulary Learning. *Arab World English Journal (AWEJ)*, Vol. 9.
- Binti Mistar, I., & Embi, M. A. (2016). Students' perception on the use of WhatsApp as a learning tool in ESL classroom. *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 4(6), 96-104.
- Bieńkowska, I. Klimczok, A. Polok, K. Modrzejewska, k (2021), Use of Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) in Teaching Vocabulary to ESP Students. *Research in Teacher Education*, 12(3): 81-95.
- Bouhnik, D., & Deshen, M. (2014). WhatsApp goes to school: Mobile instant messaging between teachers and students. *Journal of Information Technology Education. Research*, 13, 217.
- Dr. Cetinkaya L. Dr. SUTCU S. S. (2009). Students' Success In English Vocabulary Acquisition Through Multimedia Annotations Sent Via WhatsApp. *Distance Education-TOJDE*, Vol.20(4),86-96.
- Gamji, M. B. U., & Salman, J. H. (2019). Use of WhatsApp as a Learning Tool in Today's Generation: A study of Undergraduate students. *International Journal of Information Processing and Communication*, 7(1), 11.

- Gon, S., & Rawekar, A. (2017). Effectivity of e-learning through WhatsApp as a teaching learning tool. *MVP Journal of Medical Sciences*, 19-25.
- Hani, N. A. B. (2014). THE IMPACT OF WHATSAPP GROUP'S UTILIZATION ON EFL STUDENTS' VOCABULARY WRITING AMELIORATION. *International Journal of University Teaching and Faculty Development*, 5(2), 73.
- Hashemifardnia, A. Namazianadost, E., & Eshfahani, f. R. (2018). The Effect of Using WhatsApp on Iranian EFL Learners' Vocabulary Learning. *Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 5(3), 256-267.
- Khan, R. M. I., Radzuan, N. R. M., Farooqi, S. U. H., Shahbaz, M., & Khan, M. S. (2021). Learners' Perceptions on WhatsApp Integration as a Learning Tool to Develop EFL Vocabulary for Speaking Skill. *International Journal of Language Education*, 5(2), 1-14.
- Koole, M., & Ally, M. (2006, April). Framework for the rational analysis of mobile education (FRAME) model: Revising the ABCs of educational practices. In *International Conference on Networking, International Conference on Systems and International Conference on Mobile Communications and Learning Technologies (ICNICONSMCL'06)* (pp. 216-216). IEEE.
- La Hanisi, A., Risdiany, R., Dwi Utami, Y., & Sulisworo, D. (2018). The use of WhatsApp in collaborative learning to improve English teaching and learning process. *International Journal of Research Studies in Educational Technology*, 7(1), 29-35.
- Malecela, I. O. (2016). Usage of WhatsApp among postgraduate students of kulliyah of Education, International Islamic University Malaysia. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 3(10), 236879.
- Mbukusa, N. R. (2018). Perceptions of Students on the Use of WhatsApp in Teaching Methods of English as Second Language at the University of Namibia. *Journal of Curriculum and Teaching*, 7(2), 112-119.
- Nawaila, M. B., & Bicen, H. (2018). WhatsApp as a tool for distance learning. *Ponte Journal*, 74(1).
- Orij, A., & Anikpo, F. (2019). Social media in teaching-learning process: Investigation of the use of Whatsapp in teaching and learning in the University of Port Harcourt. *European Scientific Journal*, 15(4), 15-39.
- Sayan, H. (2016). Affecting higher students learning activity by using WhatsApp. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 4(3), 88-93.
- Smit, I. (2015, October). WhatsApp with learning preferences? In *2015 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

7.1. Appendix A: Questionnaire

Analyzing the student's perceptions and opinions regarding WhatsApp learning.

Dear Participant(s),

I would like to thank you for agreeing to participate in my research project on the protocol: An investigation of using WhatsApp for Learning and Teaching Vocabulary at the Tertiary Level at Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University Shaheedbenziraabad, Pakistan.

The rationale of this adopted questionnaire script from the key paper is to examine the students' attitudes towards the use of WhatsApp to enhance their vocabulary learning and the extent of learning and teaching at the tertiary level improved by using WhatsApp as a learning tool.

Please select the numbers below that best represent how you feel about your recent vocabulary learning with WhatsApp for each statement. This gained result will be used as a part of a Bs_ English thesis. It should take approximately 20 minutes.

1. Gender: Male/Female _____

2. Study at (Dept.): _____

3. Age _____

4. Batch _____

5. BS. --- M.A. ---

Coded as: (Likert Scale 5-1) 5= Strongly Agree; 4= Agree; 3= Neutral; 2= Disagree ; 1= Strongly Disagree

Items	Strongly disagree 5	Disagree 4	Undecided 3	Agree 2	Strongly agree 1
1. Learning new words using WhatsApp is an interesting method of learning.					
2. I feel more motivated to complete my vocab assignment using WhatsApp.					
3. I enjoyed learning new vocab using WhatsApp.					
4. If given the choice between using WhatsApp and the paper and pencil method of learning in future, I would choose using WhatsApp.					
5. Using WhatsApp helps me remember the new words.					
6. Writing sentences including the new words and sending them to the instructor via WhatsApp is a useful activity.					
7. Usage of mobile phones can be helpful for students.					
8. With the help of mobile we can learn many things at a time.					
9. In future, I can learn many things with WhatsApp.					
10. WhatsApp is proven as an applicable app.					
11. We can save our time in teaching and learning with mobile.					
12. Mobile phones are common today, and students are interested in studying with them.					
13. Teachers can also use mobile to make many enjoyable strategies for the students.					
14. WhatsApp is helpful to save time and develop our interest in learning vocabulary.					
15. Students show a good performance by using WhatsApp.					

THANK YOU

7.2. Appendix B

Topic: An investigation of using WhatsApp for Learning and Teaching Vocabulary at the tertiary Level

This is a list of 60 words to design a vocabulary pre-test and post-test for my research members.

I will make a quiz of different styles i.e. Grammar correction, filling the blanks with the correct word and choosing an option among 4.

1. Abstemious: not self-indulgent	21. Diminution: reduction in size /value	41. Levity: humor/frivolity
2. Abstruse: difficult to understand	22. Disputatious: argumentative	42. Miserly: like a miser (a scrooge or skinflint)
3. Abhor: find repugnant / disgust	23. Eclectic: a mix of various ideas/style	43. Morose: sullen and ill tempered
4. Acuity: keenness of thought	24. Enervating: exhausting	44. Phlegmatic: unemotional/stoic
5. Alacrity: promptness / Haste	25. Ephemeral: short-lived/fleeting	45. Precocious: developed early or quickly
6. Altruistic: unselfishly concerned for others	26. Ersatz: a poor substitute	46. Profusion: an excess/idealistic
7. Ambivalent: conflicted (feelings) / mixed thought	27. Equivocal: ambiguous/questionable	47. Quandary: a dilemma
8. Analogous: comparable/similar	28. Exonerate: to absolve/acquit	48. Quixotic: unrealistic/idealistic
9. Ascetic: a self-discipline person (like a monk)	29. Extol: to praise	49. Rancor: bitterness/resentment
10. Astute: shrewd or sly/smart	30. Facetious: cleverly amusing / bantering	50. Rebuttal: to refute
11. Belie: to contradict / disguise	31. Fastidious: unwarranted/uncalled for	51. Reprove: reprimand
12. Brevity: concise/Quick	32. Frivolous: carefree/useless	52. Repudiate: refuse to accept/be associated with
13. Capricious: impulsive/whimsical	33. Furtive: secretive / avoiding of attention	53. Reticence: restrain / reluctant
14. Censure: disapproval	34. Gratuitous: sly/cunning	54. Sanguine: optimistic/cheerful
15. Corroborate: to confirm / support	35. Impugn: to attack as wrong/false	55. Succinct: concise/brief
16. Deference: humble submission/respect	36. Inane: silly or stupid	56. Superfluous: more than enough
17. Depravity: moral corruption	37. Incurable: cannot be corrected/improved	57. Surreptitious: clandestine/secret
18. Deprecate : to disapprove of	38. Insipid: bland or lacking in flavour / interest	58. Taciturn: reserved / silent
19. Despondent: in low spirits	39. Intrepid: dauntless/fearless	59. Trite: unoriginal
20. Didactic: instructive(very)	40. Laconic: brief / to the point	60. Vacillate: indecisive

7.3. Appendix C

Pre and post-test for the students in both groups (control group and experimental).

Pre-test

1. Gender: Male/Female _____

2. Study at (Dept.): _____

3. Age _____

4. Batch _____
 5. BS. ~ MA . ~

Fill the gap in sentences by using the words mentioned below.

Fastidious, Furtive, Gratuitous, Impugn, Frivolous.

1. He wasin his preparation for the big day.
2. She has anature and won't take anything seriously.
3. There was somethingabout his actions.
4. There's too much crime and..... violence on TV.
5. I did not mean to her professional abilities.

2. Select the right answer.

1. What is another word which means the same as 'Abstemious'?

A. not self-indulgent	B. self-indulgent
C. immoderate	D. hunger

2. Find the option which has the same meaning as 'Abstruse'.

A. difficult to understand	B. comprehensible
C. concrete	D. not sure

3. What is another word for 'Abhor'?

A. find repugnant	B. disgust
C. both A&B	D. not sure

4. Choose the right option which has the same meaning as 'Acuity'

A. stupidity of thought	B. sharpness of thought
C. keenness of thought	D. not sure

5. What is the synonym of the word 'Alacrity'?

A. dullness	B. promptness/haste
C. slowness	D. not sure

3. Match the word with the correct definition.

Reprove
Taciturn
Succinct
Superfluous

concise/brief
reserved / silent
more than enough
reprimand

Post-test

1. Gender: Male/Female _____
2. Study at (Dept.): _____
3. Age _____
4. Batch _____
5. BS. ~
- Ma . ~

1. Fill the gap in sentences by using words mentioned below.

Fastidious, Furtive, Gratuitous, Impugn, Frivolous.

1. He wasin his preparation for the big day.
2. She has anature and won't take anything seriously.
3. There was somethingabout his actions.
4. There's too much crime and..... violence on TV.
5. I did not mean to her professional abilities.

2. Select the right answer.

1. Find the option which has the same meaning as 'Abstruse'.

A. comprehensible	B. concrete
C. difficult to understand	D. not sure

2. What is another word which means the same as 'Abstemious'?

A. self-indulgent	B. hunger
C. immoderate	D. not self-indulgent

3. What is the synonym of the word 'Alacrity'?

A. promptness / haste	B. slowness
C. dullness	D. not sure

4. What is another word for 'Abhor'?

A. find repugnant	B. disgust
C. both A&B	D. not sure

5. Choose the right option which has same meaning as 'Acuity'

A. stupidity of thought	B. sharpness of thought
C. keenness of thought	D. not sure

3. Match the word with correct definition.

Taciturn	concise / brief
Superfluous	reserved / silent
Reprove	more than enough
Succinct	Reprimand

Thank you

7.4. Appendix D

Week-base vocabulary exercises.

week.1

EXERCISE

1. What is another word which means the same as ‘Abstemious’?

A. not self-indulgent	B. self-indulgent
C. immoderate	D. hunger

2. Find the option which has the same meaning as ‘Abstruse’.

A. difficult to understand	B. comprehensible
C. concrete	D. not sure

3. What is another word for ‘Abhor’?

A. find repugnant	B. disgust
C. both A&B	D. not sure

4. Choose the right option which has the same meaning as ‘Acuity’:

A. stupidity of thought	B. sharpness of thought
C. keenness of thought	D. not sure

5. What is the synonym of the word ‘Alacrity’?

A. dullness	B. promptness / haste
C. slowness	D. not sure

6. Select one of given below which defines word ‘Altruistic’.

A. unselfishly concerned for others	B. self-centered
C. openhanded	D. greedy

7. Which is the right answer that defines a word, ‘Ambivalent’?

A. expressing decided feeling	B. same feelings
C. both A&B	D. conflicted (feelings)/ mixed thought

8. Find the word that has the same meaning as 'Analogous'.

A. comparable	B. similar
C. both A&B	D. not sure

9. How do you define word 'Ascetic'?

A. a self-discipline person (like a monk)	B. not within a reasonable limit
C. self-indulgent person	D. not sure

10. Find the word that has the same meaning as 'Astute':

A. shrewd or sly	B. dumb or stupid
C. naive	D. both B&C

Thank you

Week.2

EXERCISE

1. What is another word which means the same as 'Belie'?

A. represent falsely	B. to contradict.
C. to deny	D. all of them

2. Which word gives you the same meaning as 'Brevity'?

A. concise	B. quick
C. both A&B	D. N.O.T

3. Which is a suitable synonym of 'Capricious': impulsive / whimsical

A. impulsive / whimsical	B. reasonable/ cautious
C. constant/ stable	D. not sure

4. What is another word can be used instead of 'Censure': disapproval

A. approval	B. disapproval
C. agree	D. compliment

5. What is meant by 'Corroborate'?

A. contradict	B. Reject
C. to confirm	D. deny

6. Choose a correct option to similar 'Deference'.

A. disrespect	B. opposition
C. humble submission	D. not sure

7. Which is the right definition of the word 'Depravity'?

A. to disapprove of	B. humble submission/respect
C. moral corruption	D. argumentative.

8. Which one is the right meaning of 'Deprecate'?

A. to disapprove of	B. to approve of
C. both A&B	D. N.O.T

9. Select a similar meaning of the word 'Despondent'.

A. in low spirits	B. hapless
C. both A&B	D. not sure

10. What is another word which means the same as 'Didactic'?

A. instructive (very)	B. executive
C. advisory	D. both A&C

THANK YOU

Week: 3

Exercise: 3

Fill the gap in the sentence by using these words mention below.

Extol, Facetious, Ephemeral, Ersatz, Diminution, Equivocal, Exonerate, Disputatious, Eclectic, Enervating

1. The company suffered a in profit.
2. They go in for querulous and argument.
3. She has very tastes in literature.
4. A hot climate people who are not used to it.
5. Fame in the world of rock and pop is largely.....
6. Like everything else the restaurant served, the whipped cream on the dessert was.....
7. Many were about the idea.
8. He was from all responsibility for the accident.
9. Songs of the motherland are ringing far and near.
10. Stop being; this is serious.

Thank you

Week: 4

Exercise: 4

Fill the gap in sentences by using the words mentioned below.

Fastidious, Incurable, Insipid, Intrepid, Laconic, Furtive, Gratuitous, Impugn, Inane, Frivolous.

1. He wasin his preparation for the big day.
2. She has anature and won't take anything seriously.
3. There was somethingabout his actions.
4. There's too much crime and..... violence on TV.
5. I did not mean to her professional abilities.
6. There are too manyquiz shows on television these days.

7. Because he was ancriminal, he was sentenced to life imprisonment.
8. Canned coffees taste either harsh or
9. To be an astronaut, you must be an person who craves adventure and is not afraid of heights.
10. To save valuable time, give me aexplanation of what happened.

Thank you

Week: 5

Exercise

The act of refuting something by making a contrary argument/ to refute.
A feeling or long-lasting ire for another/ bitterness
Acting with the desire to do noble and romantic deeds/ unrealistic or idealistic.
A state of not knowing what to decide, a dilemma.
An excess of something or abundance.
Developed early or quickly.
Having an unemotional and stolidly calm disposition.
Sullen and ill-tempered.
Very cautious with money, like a miser.
The treatment of a serious matter with humour or lack of due respect.

Match the word with the correct definition.

1. Levity
2. Miserly
3. morose
4. Precocious
5. Phlegmatic
6. Quandary
7. Profusion
8. Quixotic
9. Rancor
10. Rebuttal

4. Surreptitious
5. Repudiate
6. Succinct
7. Vacillate
8. Taciturn
9. Reticence
10. Superfluous

Thank you